

DEFECT-BASED ASSESSMENT OF MECHANICAL AND CORROSIVE LOADS ON THE CAPABILITY OF LIGHT METAL STRUCTURES

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Light metal structures, specifically those made from aluminium and magnesium alloys, have emerged as fundamental materials in various industries due to their exceptional strength-to-weight ratios. In real-world applications, these structures are exposed to a range of complex mechanical and corrosive loads. However, the presence of defects within these materials can substantially impact their capability and durability. These defects manifest in diverse forms, depending on the specific material and environmental conditions. This study delves profoundly into the different types of defects within light metal structures and how they intricately influence these materials under varying load conditions. The investigations concentrate on two specific defect scenarios: inner, elongated defects in solid-state recycled, extruded aluminium, and corrosion pits in magnesium for biomedical applications. Both defect scenarios are considered using the fracture mechanics concept according to Murakami and Endo by measuring one or more defects, allowing a correlation of the cyclic stress intensity factor with the number of cycles to failure obtained in constant amplitude tests. Depending on the defect scenario, however, two approaches are used for considering the number of defects. This procedure, combined with innovative testing methodologies, advanced measurement techniques, and sophisticated modelling and simulation approaches, demonstrates that corrosion-induced defects can be evaluated by the fracture mechanics model in the same way as process-induced defects, enabling a holistic understanding of the materials' capabilities.

Keywords: Solid-state recycling, Aluminium alloys, Magnesium alloys, Corrosion fatigue, Biodegradable implants, Fracture mechanics

INTRODUCTION

Light metals, most notably aluminium and magnesium alloys, are pivotal in industries where weight reduction is paramount (Apelian et al. [1]). Their exceptional strength-to-weight ratios and their property spectra make them indispensable in sectors such as automotive, aerospace, and biomedicine and help to prevent global challenges like climate change and aging society (Shamsudin et al. [2]). However, the capability of these structures is intricately linked to the presence of defects, which can manifest in various forms depending on the material and environmental factors. These defects, whether they are inner delaminations in aluminium, corrosion pits in magnesium, or stress concentrations in complex geometries, pose significant challenges for responsible component design

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(Boehm et al. [3]). This compels the development of sophisticated testing strategies, novel measurement techniques, and state-of-the-art modelling to holistically assess the materials' capabilities.

Aluminium, renowned for its remarkable properties, is gaining prominence in applications due to its high strength, corrosion resistance, and formability. As its use in industries like automotive and aerospace continues to grow, driven by environmental concerns and resource constraints, efficient production and recycling methods are of increasing importance [1]. While aluminium's benefits are evident, its production remains energy-intensive and costly, significantly surpassing the energy requirements of steel production (Worell et al. [4]). The solution lies in aluminium recycling, a more sustainable alternative that conserves energy and yields secondary aluminium with properties akin to primary aluminium (Gronostajski and Matuszak [5]). To achieve even more energy savings, researchers are exploring solid-state recycling processes, particularly focusing on aluminium chips, which not only reduce material costs but also minimise losses compared to conventional recycling (Wan et al. [6]). In these solid-state recycling processes, aluminium chips undergo bonding below the melting point, relying on welding and diffusion mechanisms. The key challenge is ensuring a high-quality interface between individual chips by disrupting the oxide layers that encase them, facilitating proper metal-to-metal contact. Two primary approaches are employed: severe plastic deformation (SPD) processes, applying high strain and pressure, and diffusion-based field-assisted sintering (FAST) processes conducted at room temperature ([6], Ab Rahim et al. [7], Soo et al. [8]). Both SPD and FAST processes cause elongated defects due to the strain the production processes induce. The central research focus is adapting fatigue lifetime models to accommodate these elongated defects in aluminium structures since fracture mechanics-based fatigue lifetime models deal with round defects (Gronostajski et al. [9], Koch et al. [10]). Computed tomography (CT) analysis of specimens plays a critical role in evaluating defect distribution, determining the criticality of single defects, and identifying the initiating defect size. This is essential for estimating fatigue life based on the stress intensity factor derived from defect distribution data obtained through CT scans (Koch et al. [11], Siegfanz et al. [12]). This research advances the understanding of aluminium recycling processes and supports sustainable aluminium applications across industries.

Biodegradable implants, e.g., made of magnesium, zinc, or iron, are designed for temporary support of the human body, and take advantage of the inherent biodegradability of these materials in aqueous environments (Han et al. [13]). However, their low corrosion resistance, which may be disadvantageous in technical applications, must be precisely understood in terms of long-time corrosion behaviour, corrosion morphology, the effect of corrosion pits as surface defects, and the associated reduction in mechanical stability (Clausius et al. [14]). Of the metals mentioned, current research focuses on magnesium (Mg) because of its biocompatibility, mechanical properties comparable to the cortical bone, and natural occurrence as a bulk element in the human body (Niranjan et al. [15]). Thereby, magnesium corrodes in water-based electrolytes, forming hydrogen gas and magnesium hydroxide. The reaction rate (i.e., corrosion rate) can be determined by detecting the hydrogen gas volume or by ex situ measurement of the weight loss after the removal of the corrosion layer (Song and Atrens [16]). Only the hydrogen gas method allows an in situ measurement during immersion tests since the removal of the corrosion layer influences the subsequent corrosion process (Zheng et al. [17]). In addition to the corrosion rate, the corrosion morphology has a significant influence on the long-time stability of Mg implants since local corrosion acts as a notch and, thus, leads to increased stress intensity factors (Raman et al. [18]). Different mechanisms lead to localised corrosion under superimposed corrosive-mechanical loading but also under singular corrosive loading. The magnesium hydroxide layer has no inherent stability and is additionally deteriorated by chloride-containing electrolytes (such as human blood) (Staiger et al. [19]). Due to the low electrochemical standard potential of magnesium, the α -Mg matrix acts as an anode towards almost any secondary

phase or impurity and is preferentially dissolved through micro-galvanic corrosion (Bian et al. [20]). Under superimposed fatigue loading, the formation of intrusions and extrusions also plays a role, as does the stiffness difference between the corrosion layer and the substrate material, as this can additionally break down the magnesium hydroxide layer (Gu et al. [21], Han et al. [22]). The existing studies on the in vitro corrosion fatigue behaviour of Mg alloys report a drastic decrease in corrosion fatigue strength compared to the reference tests in air ([21], Jafari et al. [23]). Regardless of the alloy system, cracks initiate at localised weak spots when reaching a critical size and stress intensity factor (Liu et al. [24], Zhao et al. [25]). In addition to these mechanisms, hydrogen embrittlement is reported at the crack tip, in turn increasing the crack propagation rate [23]. Since the characterisation of in vitro corrosion fatigue properties for implantation periods of several weeks is time-consuming and hardly feasible, research is being carried out on short-time testing methods. In this context, galvanostatic polarisation (GSP) offers the possibility to accelerate corrosion and, thus, to reproduce longer immersion times. The relationship between the current density during GSP, the mass loss, and the hydrogen volume is linear so that the corrosion rate can be regulated accordingly (Shi et al. [26], Shi et al. [27], Huang et al. [28]). This relationship was used to replicate the long-time corrosion and corrosion fatigue behaviour and to characterise the influence of this method on the corrosion morphology using a defect-based approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Elongated defects in solid-state-recycled aluminium

In the context of solid-state-recycled aluminium chips, the quality of bonding between individual chips interconnected through microstructural welding plays a pivotal role in determining the quality of the final profiles. Inadequate welding leads to inner defects, particularly delaminations. The distribution of these defects was meticulously characterised using a combination of computed tomography and electrical resistance measurements. Furthermore, the effects of these defects on quasi-static and cyclic properties were estimated through mechanical testing and defect-based modelling and simulation. Details can be found in [10].

Specimens were taken from bulk EN AW-6082 aluminium alloy, and milled chips were used for solid-state recycling. The chemical composition met DIN EN 573-3 standards (**Table 1**). To avoid issues with chip welding due to cooling lubricants, a dry milling process was employed, resulting in chips with an average size of $10.5 \times 1.1 \times 0.3 \text{ mm}^3$ and a bulk density of 0.3 g/cm^3 .

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of EN AW-6082, determined by EDX, compared with standard.

Ref.	Si	Cu	Fe	Mn	Mg	Zn	Ti	Al
DIN EN 573-3	0.7-1.3	< 0.1	< 0.5	0.4-1.0	0.6-1.2	< 0.2	< 0.1	Bal.
EDX	1.11	-	0.41	0.62	1.11	-	-	Bal.

The solid-state recycling process involved three steps. Initially, the chips were pre-compacted at 100 MPa pressure, resulting in a green compact density of 1.6 g/cm^3 . FAST was then used to bond the green compacts into semi-finished blanks. The applied static pressure during FAST was varied (80 MPa for state B and 40 MPa for state A), and the relative density of the sintered blanks reached about 99%. The milled chip microstructure remained visible due to the short cycle times. After FAST, the blanks were sandblasted, coated with graphite lubricant, and prepared for forward rod extrusion (FRE) at room temperature. The resulting extrudates were subjected to T6 heat treatment.

Cyclic investigations of solid-state recycled aluminium chips were conducted using cold-extruded, heat-treated shafts, where the shaft's uniform microstructure resulted from homogeneous deformation during FRE. The shafts had a diameter of 16 mm and a length of approximately 90 mm, sufficient for extracting fatigue specimens. The fatigue investigations were performed using an Instron 8872 servohydraulic fatigue testing system ($f = 10$ Hz, $N_{\text{limit}} = 2 \cdot 10^6$) and a Rumul Gigaforte 50 resonant fatigue testing system ($f = 1,000$ Hz, $N_{\text{limit}} = 10^9$). [10]

Corrosion pits in magnesium implants

The results presented are an excerpt from the research work “In vitro short-time testing method for evaluating the long-time corrosion fatigue strength of biomedical magnesium alloys” (Wegner et al. [29]) which are extended to include a defect-based approach for evaluation of the short-time testing method. For the detailed experimental procedure, please refer to the mentioned paper.

The short-time testing method was applied to the unmodified and plasma electrolytic oxidation PEO-modified (Kermasorb[®], Meotec, Aachen, Germany) Mg alloy WE43 (Meotec, Aachen, Germany) with an elemental composition containing 1.4-4.2% Y, 2.5-3.5% Nd, less than 1% of Al, Fe, Cu, Ni, Mn, Zn, Zr, and balance Mg (in wt.%). The cylindrical specimens used have a gauge length of 9 mm and an initial diameter of 4 mm, which was separated via an anti-corrosion lacquer to provide a defined area. The alloy has a fine, inhomogeneous microstructure with a high number of intermetallic precipitates of different sizes (ranging from ca. 50 nm to a few micrometres) and shapes (round, rod-shaped, branched), occurring elongated by the extrusion process parallel to the extrusion direction (ED, **Figure 1a**). The PEO-layer exhibits the process typical high porosity and brittleness (i.e., cracks) and has a thickness of 25 ± 4 μm (**Figure 1b**). Pores occurring in or at the interface to the substrate material are to be considered critical with respect to mechanical stresses.

FIGURE 1 SEM images of the longitudinal section of WE43 without (a), and with (b) plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO-) layer.

The corrosion behaviour of both material variants was investigated in immersion tests with a duration of three weeks at open circuit potential (OCP) in a modified minimum essential medium (mMEM, 1% glutamine, 1% penicillin/streptomycin, 1% fungizone) at 36.5 °C. Thereby, the specific hydrogen volume $V_{\text{H}_2, \text{spec}}$ was detected, and the corrosion morphology was subsequently characterised by means of scanning electron microscopy at cross sections of the specimens. The hydrogen evolution rate (HER) was used to calculate the corrosion rate $\dot{m}_{\text{corr, OCP}}$, and the results were divided into three regions, each with an approximately constant corrosion rate (Hartjen et al. [30], Wegner and Walther [31], Wegner et al. [32]). In preliminary studies, under simplified conditions, including the use of a less complex electrolyte (0.9% NaCl solution, 36.5 °C), the relationship between the current density i under GSP, corrosion rate (via HER), and corrosion morphology was determined. This relationship is given for both material variants via equation 1 with $A_2 = 1.094$ for both, $A_1 = 3.372$ for WE43, and $A_1 = 3.139$ for WE43 PEO [31, 32] and was used to calculate the current densities required to

simulate the corrosion progress of the immersion tests with a duration of $t_{\text{OCP}} = 21$ days ($= t_{\text{sim}}$) within $t_{\text{GSP}} = 3$ days.

$$i = A2 \sqrt{\dot{m}_{\text{corr,OCP}} \cdot \frac{t_{\text{OCP}}}{t_{\text{GSP}}} \cdot 10^{A1}} \quad (1)$$

Fracture mechanics-based approach

In terms of structural integrity, evaluating the criticality of defects is vital for understanding their impact on mechanical properties. Linear elastic fracture mechanics serves as the foundation for this investigation. The stress intensity factor range ΔK is employed to estimate the fatigue life based on defect characteristics. As per established principles, ΔK is determined using equation 2. Where Y is a geometric factor (e.g., 0.5 for inner defects), $\Delta\sigma$ is the stress range, and 'a' represents the crack length. According to Murakami and Endo [33], the crack length can be estimated using the projected defect area perpendicular to the load direction, as expressed in equation 3, but other characteristic values than the projected area are discussed.

$$\Delta K_I = Y \cdot \Delta\sigma \cdot \sqrt{\pi \cdot a} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta K_I = Y \cdot \Delta\sigma \cdot \sqrt{\pi \cdot \sqrt{\text{area}}} \quad (3)$$

Various characteristic values are employed to assess defects, but aligning defects in a specific direction, like in the case of extrusion, can complicate their assessment using conventional parameters. In such scenarios, the approach of Murakami and Endo, focussing on the projected defect area, which plays a pivotal role in understanding the criticality of defects, has to be adapted to elongated defects (Redik et al. [34]). One commonly used characteristic value for evaluating defects is the equivalent defect diameter d_e (equation 4). It is defined as the diameter of an ideal sphere with the same volume V as the corresponding defect. This parameter is frequently used to assess the impact of defects, such as pores, on the mechanical properties of materials.

$$d_e = \sqrt[3]{\frac{6 \cdot V}{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

The distribution of the equivalent defect diameter often follows a log-normal distribution, a common trend in defect distributions in various materials. The choice of characteristic value depends on the nature of the defects and their alignment. For defects that align with the loading direction, it becomes critical to consider their projected defect area perpendicular to the loading direction. This approach recognises that, especially in the case of elongated defects, the defect's volume has less impact on the projected area compared to the equivalent defect diameter. For defects aligned in a specific direction, this parameter becomes crucial. When defects are aligned in a certain direction, differences between materials or conditions can become more apparent by accounting for the squared effect of diameter in an area-based characteristic value (Smith and Miller [35]). Therefore, Murakami's concept has to be adapted to elongated defects.

RESULTS

Elongated defects in solid-state-recycled aluminium

The results presented are an excerpt from the research work "Computed tomography-based defect characterization and prediction of fatigue properties of extrudates from recycled field-assisted sintered EN AW-6082 aluminium chips" (Koch et al. [10]).

Parts of the results have already been published in [10, 31].

The characterisation of defect distribution, achieved through computed tomography and electrical resistance measurements [10], provided insights into the effects of the process parameters on the local quality of the chip boundaries. Modelling and simulation approaches successfully estimated the impact of defects on mechanical properties, enhancing the determination of their influence.

Figure 2 illustrates volume reconstructions for states A and B, revealing differences in defect characteristics. State A exhibits more large defects, while state B has a higher number of small defects, with increased defect scattering in state A. This discrepancy highlights substantial variation in defect distribution for state A, making it evident that the best state A specimens have defects nearly as critical as the worst state B specimens. No defects were detected in reference specimens. Notably, delaminations primarily align with the extrusion direction, posing a challenge in assessing the criticality of defects using common characteristic values. State A shows a higher maximum equivalent defect diameter (962 μm) than state B (549 μm), but state B has more small defects in total. In contrast, Murakami and Endo emphasise the relevance of defect areas perpendicular to the loading direction for assessing critical defects, particularly for the fracture mechanics concept applied in this study. Previous investigations [10] showed that the distribution of the projected defect area can be described by a linear relationship in a log-log scale.

Volume reconstructions - State A		Volume (μm^3) 2E8 1E8 0			
	0.24	0.28	0.14	1.65	
Volume reconstructions - State B		Volume (μm^3) 2E8 1E8 0			
	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.14	

FIGURE 2 Defect distributions of chip-based specimens (gage length section), EN AW-6082 [10].

In the pursuit of estimating the fatigue life of chip-based specimens, it becomes critical to determine the size of defects that act as crack initiators. To evaluate the applicability of Murakami's approach, particularly in situations involving elongated defects, it has to be compared how different defect characteristics, such as size, shape, and edge distance, can influence the crack initiation process and, ultimately, the fatigue life of the specimens, explaining the high scatter in the SN-curve (**Figure 3a**). In this context, the size of the defect responsible for crack initiation is estimated through statistical considerations. By assessing different fractions of defects, the investigations aim to identify the most appropriate defect characteristic value for estimating fatigue life based on ΔK . The proposed approach involves averaging the sizes of the largest defects, thereby excluding small defects that may not contribute significantly to crack initiation. This method also accounts for very large defects that, although critical, may not be located in surface-critical regions. The study examines the coefficient of determination for the regression line of the ΔK -N-diagram for varying numbers of averaged largest defects (**Figure 3b**). The results demonstrate that averaging different defect fractions leads to

improved coefficients of determination up to a certain number of defects. Notably, the equivalent defect diameter and the projected defect area are compared to determine the best-suited defect characteristic value. The study concludes that averaging the largest defects, particularly using the equivalent defect diameter, provides the best coefficient of determination. This highlights that the largest defect does not initiate the crack in most cases, raising questions about the accuracy of averaging such high numbers of defects for estimating crack initiation.

FIGURE 3 S-N-diagram for states A and B compared to the reference material EN AW-6082-T6 (a), coefficient of determination of ΔK -N-curves for different fractions of defects (b) [10].

FIGURE 4 ΔK -N-curves with mean of largest 200 ($P_{z,mean}$) defects as a basis for the estimation of the crack initiating defect characteristic value (a), comparison between estimated and experimental results of fatigue tests (b), EN AW-6082-T6 [10].

Despite the challenges posed by the inability to measure the size of crack-initiating defects post-testing, the results suggest that averaging the largest defects can serve as a basis for estimating fatigue life based on pre-test CT scans. The equivalent defect diameter and the projected defect area yield similar results, with the former offering the best coefficient of determination. By employing equation 5, which correlates the stress intensity factor range and the number of cycles to failure, the fatigue

life of FAST-recycled specimens can be calculated based on corresponding CT scans. **Figure 4** presents the results, indicating that the fatigue life can be calculated with sufficient accuracy. Intriguingly, regardless of the specimen's state of origin, both states follow the same regression line.

$$N_f = \sqrt[{-0.1248}]{\frac{0.5 \cdot \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\text{MPa}} \cdot \pi \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{d_{e,mean,150}}{\mu\text{m}}\right)^2}}{16.0826}} \quad (5)$$

The investigations show that averaging provides a good estimation of the fatigue life, making it possible to estimate the crack initiating defect based on the CT scans without having to determine it retrospectively from SEM images. However, the necessity of averaging also clarifies that strongly elongated defects do not allow the use of the Murakami concept, neither of the equivalent defect diameter nor of the projected defect area.

Corrosion pits in magnesium implants

The short-time testing method using GSP allows the behaviours to be qualitatively reproduced, with a slightly lower specific hydrogen volume for the substrate material WE43 (-21%) and a slightly higher hydrogen volume for the PEO-modified WE43 (+17%). The corrosion morphology of the substrate material exhibits a uniform corrosion morphology for a majority of the specimens (**Figure 5a**), with individual specimens undergoing significant pitting (**Figure 5b**). The occurrence of local corrosion is subjected to a statistical probability, increasing with the number and size of precipitates and with increasing immersion time (Ascencio et al. [36]). In contrast, the PEO-modified specimens do not show any local corrosion; there is only a dissolution of the layer and an increase in the pore size. Under GSP, all specimens of both material variants exhibit significant pitting, enhancing the pitting tendency of WE43 and changing the corrosion mechanism of the PEO-modified variant.

FIGURE 5 SEM images of the cross section of WE43 (a), and after corrosion at open circuit potential (OCP) (b).

To determine the influence of increased pitting on the corrosion fatigue properties, constant amplitude tests (CAT) were performed with and without GSP at a stress ratio of $R = -1$ up to a maximum number of cycles of $N_{limit} = 2 \cdot 10^6$ (**Figure 6a**). The frequency of the reference tests in air was set to $f = 10$ Hz, and for the tests in the electrolyte, the frequency was adjusted according to the targeted immersion time. **Figure 6b** shows the fatigue and corrosion fatigue strength with and without GSP of both material variants over the immersion time. In air and for an immersion time of 2 days, hardly any differences between the material variants are discernible. The slightly higher fatigue strength of the substrate material ($\sigma_{a,fs,WE43} = 180$ MPa, $\sigma_{a,fs,PEO} = 175$ MPa) is explained by the high number of pores and cracks in the brittle PEO-layer and the associated premature crack initiation (Němcová et al. [37]). For an immersion time of 2 days, the effects of higher corrosion resistance and crack initiation

in the PEO-layer seem to compensate one another (140 MPa). For longer immersion times, the effect of the higher corrosion resistance dominates, resulting in the PEO-modified variant achieving a higher corrosion fatigue strength (130 MPa to 110 MPa). Resulting of the increased formation of corrosion pits under GSP, a significant reduction in corrosion fatigue properties of both material variants occurs. Corrosion fatigue strengths of 50 MPa (WE43) and 40 MPa (PEO) are determined for an immersion time of $t_{GSP} = 4/7$ days, intended to simulate an immersion time of $t_{sim} = 4$ days. These values are significantly lower than the reference values from the corrosion fatigue tests at OCP for $t_{OCP} = 4$ days with 110 MPa (WE43) and 130 MPa (PEO).

To understand the influence of corrosion and surface modification by PEO, the S-N-diagram is presented in **Figure 6b** as a result of the fatigue tests. Notably, this diagram reveals a strong scattering of data points, primarily attributed to varying immersion times and associated corrosion pit formation, as previously observed in **Figure 5b**. It becomes evident that samples subjected to longer corrosion durations exhibit significantly shorter fatigue lifespans. Moreover, the introduction of the protective surface modification has a positive impact on extending the material's fatigue life, owing to the mitigation of corrosion-induced damage.

FIGURE 6 (Corrosion) fatigue strength for different immersion times at open circuit potential t_{OCP} and for simulated immersion times t_{sim} under galvanostatic polarisation (GSP) for WE43 with and without plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO) (a), and corresponding S-N-diagram (b) [32].

To delve deeper into the defect-based approach, Murakami's fracture mechanics concept was used, akin to the methodologies applied previously at aluminium. This involves a meticulous analysis of fracture surfaces via SEM to identify crack initiation points. Subsequently, the corrosion pits identified as the culprits behind crack initiation are quantified using ImageJ software. With the defect sizes in hand, equation 2 is employed to determine the associated stress intensity factor for each crack initiating defect. The results of this analysis are presented in **Figure 7a**. This figure showcases a notable reduction in the scatter found in the S-N-diagram when the data is plotted against the stress intensity factor. This observation underscores that the scattering primarily arises from the varied corrosion pits and, importantly, emphasises that the reduction in fatigue life is predominantly a consequence of the mechanical impact of corrosion pits rather than the corrosive effects themselves. This notion gains further support from the observation that both material variants align along a linear trendline, indicating that the corrosion-inhibiting properties of the PEO-modification play a minor role in extending fatigue life itself but indirectly due to the prevention of corrosion pits and high stress

intensity factors. Furthermore, in **Figure 7b**, the specific stress intensity factor (stress intensity factor divided by the stress amplitude) is plotted against immersion time, a departure from the traditional representation of fatigue lifetime. For OCP, the PEO-modified variant shows an almost linear relationship over the immersion time, whereas for WE43, an increased scatter is evident, indicating the heterogeneous corrosion behaviour. Since the PEO-modified material shows lower spec. stress intensity factors within this range, the positive influence regarding the corrosion morphology is discernible. Superimposing GSP causes the values to increase significantly and, thus, explains the reduction in corrosion fatigue strength compared to the tests at OCP. Nevertheless, the estimation of the fatigue life by the stress intensity factor is successful, showing that this value is the most relevant parameter for determining the fatigue life and the concept of Murakami can be adapted to corrosion fatigue.

FIGURE 7 Estimation of fatigue lifetime of WE43 with and without plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO) based on stress intensity factor (a), and correlation of the specific stress intensity factor over the (simulated) immersion time (b).

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, it can be stated that the capability of light metal structures has to be estimated well due to high scatter under different loading conditions in the form of mechanical or corrosive loads. Combined with a different micro and defect structure, a defect-based assessment is necessary. It could be shown that by adapting Murakami's concept for different loading conditions of aluminium and magnesium, a defect-based estimation of the fatigue life is possible.

For aluminium specimens made from chips with elongated defects, an estimation of the fatigue life with high accuracy could be assessed by averaging the defects and applying the projected defect area. The scatter of both states considered could not only be significantly reduced but both states could also be described with the help of a common fatigue lifeline. In addition, CT scans could be used for the first time to estimate the critical defect in advance of the mechanical examinations. Previously, this was only possible retrospectively on the basis of fracture images by means of SEM.

For biodegradable magnesium alloys, it was found that the scatter in the S-N-diagram could be attributed solely to the notch effect resulting from the corrosion attack. By applying Murakami's

concept based on the measurement of the crack initiating corrosion pits in fractographic images, the scatter could be significantly reduced. In addition, as with aluminium, both material variants could be described with one line. As a consequence, it was also shown that the stress intensity factor despite an outlier is directly related to the immersion time, which is an important finding for further investigations, as it could be possible to directly estimate the fatigue life based on the immersion time, without the need for corrosion fatigue tests to be carried out.

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